

Manager and Personnel Hierarchy in Education Management

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Abstract

The majority of the time, these people would begin their professions as certified educators, but during the course of their careers, they would transition into other professional responsibilities within education systems. This subgroup of staff consists of all members of the staff whose major role it is to assist the academic program that the students are participating in. Additionally, it encompasses the same kinds of employees as those covered by Pedagogical Support (ISCED 0-4), in addition to covering additional professional support staff members who are employed in higher education institutions. Health care professionals such as physicians, dentists, ophthalmologists, optometrists, hygienists, nurses, and diagnosticians are included in this category. Also included are mental health professionals such as psychiatrists and psychologists, speech pathologists and audiologists, occupational therapists, and social workers. These individuals are all working in education systems and offer pupils with services that support their health as well as their social lives. This subcategory refers to professional employees whose main or major role is the administration or administration of schools. Examples include principals, assistant principals, and other administrative personnel. It is made up of managers, assistant managers, managers, assistant managers, and other management staff members who perform functions that are comparable to those of managers. It does not include the school's receptionists, secretaries, clerks, or any other employees of the school's support staff that help with the school's administrative responsibilities. Personnel bearing titles such as president, vice president, dean, director, or department head or

similar are often included in this category if their primary activity is administrative. Examples of these titles are president of the United States, vice president of the United States, and department head. One is not considered for inclusion if the principal activity they engage in is not administrative. This subcategory is comprised of individuals whose primary or primary occupation is quality control and administration of the education system at higher levels than school; hence, it is representative of management at a higher level. Some of the prospective employers of these individuals are the local boards of education, the ministries or departments of education at the state, regional, or national level, and the ministries or departments of education at the local level. Their tasks may include direct management, in addition to a variety of additional functions that are essential to the operation of educational institutions. Some examples of these responsibilities include public information, planning and assessment, budgeting and accounting, and other related activities. This group of professionals includes a wide variety of administrative jobs, including school inspectors, assistant superintendents and assistant superintendents, education superintendents, assistant and deputy teaching superintendents, and curriculum managers, planning and evaluation managers, and other positions with names very similar to these.

Keywords: *Educational Administration, Principals and School, Educational Administrators, Hierarchy in Educational Administration*

Introduction

It encompasses a wide range of extra management tasks that are particular to the field of higher education. Those individuals who lend a hand to the management and administration of the institution fall within the purview of this subcategory. Receptionists, secretaries, typists, word processors, accountants and clerks, copy helpers, and other roles are examples of the types of personnel that fall into this category. This class refers, in particular, to staff members who are employed at the school level. Accountants, analysts, auditors, computer programmers, systems analysts, evaluators, financial aid workers, grant developers, lawyers, network administrators, public relations/information services officers, registrars, and other individuals with duties and responsibilities comparable to those of the aforementioned positions are included among these other personnel. People who give help with the administrative and managerial tasks of the education system at levels higher than school are included in this subcategory. Some of the prospective employers of these individuals are the local boards of education, the ministries or departments of education at the state, regional, or national level, and the ministries or departments

of education at the local level. The term "educational personnel management" refers to a methodically planned approach for efficiently recruiting and employing workers at educational institutions, both within and outside of the buildings themselves. This is done in order to accomplish the predetermined fitness objectives that have been set. Management of personnel is an encompassing endeavor that, when successfully completed, will raise the degree of professionalism, efficiency, and effectiveness in a company. Activities that come within the purview of personnel management include, but are not limited to, the implementation of people-related tasks, functions, and obligations. Some examples of such activities include planning, buying, quality improvement, placement promotions, remuneration, and welfare, as well as layoffs. This approach needs to incorporate people management, capacity development, and the promotion of a productive work environment in order for the company to recruit and keep individuals who are competent and motivated.

Methodology

the OECD Teacher Policy Recommendation Fred C. Lunenburg (2006: 750), the people management process consists of the following processes:

- (a) recruiting,*
- (b) choosing,*
- (c) staff development and*
- (d) performance appraisal.*

Recruitment of Education Staff

Recruitment decisions are made according to the results of the calculation of the number of personnel currently on duty. When there is a deficiency as seen in Figure 7.1. OECD Teacher Policy Recommendation (OECD, 2010: 70) According to Fred C. Lunenburg (2006: 750), the people management process consists of the following processes:

- (a) recruiting,*
- (b) choosing,*

(c) staff development and

(d) performance appraisal.

The process of hiring people to fill training positions begins with staffing level planning as its foundation. The OECD cites Santiago (2004) as the source for this framework for the teacher labor market. According to William B. Castetter (1996: 86), the term "recruitment" refers to efforts in staff management that are meant to assure the quantity and quality of workers necessary to carry out the tasks required by the educational system. To fill some vacancies that are still unfilled as a result of the construction of new units, as well as the creation of new units and as a consequence of people Recruitment, recruitment of teachers and education people is being done in order to fulfill the purpose of filling certain vacancies. It is essential to ascertain whether or not there is a growing population of people who meet the prerequisites in terms of both quantity and expertise in order to complete the required tasks. The activities included in the recruiting process are reportedly supervised and coordinated by a set human resources strategy, people development plan, and selection plan, as stated by William B. Castetter (1996:125). This is the situation with the actions that are involved in the recruitment of instructors to an educational establishment. The strategy for human resources will identify the number of positions that need to be filled over the planning period. The development plan will define the capabilities of current employees to fill particular gaps, and the selection process will concentrate on eliminating applicants who do not fit the requirements for the role. As a continuation of the planning for the training of personnel, the process of recruiting consists of numerous phases, each of which is significant but not as crucial as the others. In point of fact, there will unquestionably always be some kind of link with the efficiency with which the selecting process is carried out. According to Fred C. Lunenburg (2006: 748), recruitment is described as the process of recruiting a pool of qualified applicants to an institution in order to refresh or extend its human resources. Lunenburg notes that this process may be seen of as a kind of marketing. In order to effectively attract applicants, leaders need to (a) have a complete awareness of job needs, (b) be aware of the legal constraints that impact recruitment activities, and (c) nurture prospective worker resources. The following are the actions that need to be taken in order to finish the recruiting process:

In the beginning, an announcement should be made in line with the standard operating procedure for planning for the need of educational staff members possessing a variety of different sorts of credentials. The second step is to make the application process available for registration,

either in line with the administrative criteria or the academic standards that have been established. The standard method for selecting candidates was followed for each of the three exams, and any selection strategy or individualized approach that was deemed essential was used.

From the literature

Standard selection criteria generally include factors such as age, physical health, education, experience, objectives, temperament, general knowledge, communication skills, motivation, interests, attitudes, values, mental health, and honest effort in education, among other things. The process continues with the following stage, which is the development of training personnel. This step comes after the selection and placement of applicants. According to William B. Castetter (1996: 226), the function of human resources does not end after open positions have been filled. Instead, once a person has been employed by him, it is the individual's responsibility to care about his or her own future, productivity, and demands. This covers measures relating to employee associations, complaints, staff development, health, tenure, leaves, replacement service and retirement, as well as the retirement of employees themselves. The system has built a number of processes, the human development program being the most essential of them. The aim of these procedures is to attract new staff, keep the personnel that is already there, and improve both the quality and quantity of the workforce so that the system can achieve its objectives and find solutions to its issues. (Castetter, 1996:232). As will be noted in a moment, the process of personnel development is deeply entwined with human resource planning. This is due to the fact that a successful strategy for human resources involves the following:

1. To enhance the overall performance of everyone who now holds a job in accordance with the tasks and responsibilities that they have been assigned.

2. enhancing the essential capabilities of some personnel in order to fulfill the projected demand for open jobs in the organization.

3. Foster the personal growth of each and every member of the staff in order to enhance their effect as persons and to make it easier to meet requirements.

4. It is necessary to offer a framework for identifying and developing possible successors in each employee group across the whole school system, beginning with CEOs and ending with support employees. This should begin at the top and work its way down through the employee

groups. The introduction of new duties, positions, tools, and techniques, all of which demand a higher level of knowledge, is the fundamental reason for the need to generate new skills in the workforce. This is why there is a need to create new skills in the workforce.

Personnel Development Process

The staff development approach will incorporate the career path as one of its components. Activities that are done in the near term and those that are done in the long term are both included in personnel development. Each of these subcategories of activities pursues a distinct set of aims, engages people at various strata and levels, and addresses a broad range of potential strategies for structuring the staff development function and ways of thinking about it. The gap that exists between the existing condition and the one that was planned is what gives rise to the notion that there is room for improvement. On one side of the equation, we have our needs, and on the other, we have our objectives. The issues are transformed into programs via the use of goals. According to Fred C. Lunenburg (2006: 750), schools seek and choose individuals whose credentials fit the job needs as much as feasible. Nevertheless, the match is seldom a perfect match. In many instances, it is necessary for employees at all levels, including maintenance, service, clerical, and professional, to be trained on how to apply their abilities to the requirements of a certain job in order for them to be effective in doing so. Training is a phrase that is used to describe the education that is provided to new workers in order for them to gain the essential abilities. In most contexts, the word "development" refers to the process of providing guidance to seasoned professionals on how to maintain or further enhance their existing skill sets. In its most basic form, the process of training and developing faculty and staff members consists of the following four steps:

- (1) recognizing the requirements of trainees;
- (2) deciding the goals of education;
- (3) selecting the methods to be employed; and
- (4) evaluating the program.

Personnel Development Typology (Casterter, 1996:233)

Personnel Development Typology Development Needs-Goals Effectiveness of the position
Casterter, transition Advancement in one's profession; strengthening of one's position;
enhancement of one's unit System improvement Development Groups Individuals, Groups,
Intergroups, and the Development of Organizations Process Formal and informal methods; at
work; during physical activity; learning on one's own; educational standards and guidelines.

Conceptual Framework of Development Activity

Staff development refers to the process of cultivating employees by using strategies that place an emphasis on the individuals' capacity for self-actualization, growth, and progress. The actions that individuals within a system carry out with the purpose of enhancing and broadening their existing capabilities, attitudes, abilities, and knowledge are the ones that make up growth. The aims of the individual, the goals of the group, and the goals of the institution are all included in the goals of integrated staff development. The Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) establishes connections between the professional development of educators and the labor market, educational policy, and the need for educators at the national level. There are four major stages that make to the development of the staff. First, diagnosing development needs. Second, it is essential to formulate strategies for the organization's continued expansion. The implementation of various development initiatives is the next step to take. Conducting an assessment of the staff development program is the fourth phase in the process. The process of upgrading is one of the most typical ways that workers are trained. This is something that can be done to both expand the capabilities of the workforce as well as to refresh it. Other approaches include participation in events such as workshops, seminars, panels, meetings, symposia, conferences, and other gatherings of a similar kind.

Dismissal of Education Staff

The procedure that results in education staff being unable to fulfill their job tasks or the operations of the office they work for, either temporarily or for a length of time, is the process that culminates in the personnel being dismissed from their positions. This may be for a short time or for an extended period of time. The following are examples of acceptable reasons for termination:

1. Your own individual motivation for ending the relationship.

2. You must have reached the minimum age for retirement that is required by the applicable laws.

3. The presence of a simplified organization, which, on the one hand, resulted in the simplicity of the job, resulted in the payment of surplus labor, and, on the other hand, resulted in the task itself being simplified.

4. Fraud or illegal activity.

5. fully competent neither in terms of their physical nor mental capabilities.

6. It is a violation of the relevant regulations to leave the employment before the allotted amount of time has passed.

7. Being confirmed as deceased or missing by a body that has authority over the situation.

In order to create an efficient system for the administration of education employees, there are a few procedures that need to be followed. All of this is required since they are required to guarantee not only their rights but also the training staff, which guarantees that all of the circumstances that comprise the organization are true. The procedure for firing an employee has a direct bearing on how much importance is assigned to the contribution made by education employees to the successful completion of educational objectives. In other words, when an employee is unable to work for a variety of reasons, the firm will pay attention to a wide variety of variables pertaining to the circumstance. After an employee's job has been terminated, the individual may be eligible for retirement benefits or severance pay, depending on the terms of any applicable regulations or contracts. Because this is in accordance with the rights of civilian workers who have previously served in the armed forces, the position in question has to be taken into consideration. This government has made it a priority to address both the issue of teacher shortages as well as to enhance the overall quality of education. It offers a conceptual framework that may be used to differentiate, characterize, and correlate the many factors that are involved in the management of teacher demand and supply. When considered in the light of this conversation, it is obvious that the ultimate objective is to raise the standard of education across the board. The five essential areas that are engaged are "Demand for Teachers," "Teachers' Potential Supply," "Structural Elements That Shape the Market for Teachers," the Consequent "Current Teaching Power," and "Teaching Quality," which Result from the Interaction Between "Teaching Quality"

and "Teaching Environment." The first purpose of this essay was to highlight the key policy concerns that need to be addressed. The second objective of this paper is to provide an explanation of the present empirical results on topics crucial to the management of teacher supply and demand.

Argument

The identification of a complete collection of data items that are necessary for future meaningful quantitative analysis is required, and one of the final aims is to evaluate the status of the data that is already accessible on educators in the OECD. The findings of the research that was carried out for the purpose of compiling this report led to a significant discovery, which was that the quality of the teacher is an essential factor in determining how much a student learns. As a consequence of this, the process of recruiting and keeping highly qualified instructors is critical to the growth of superior educational establishments. The widely held belief that certain countries in the OECD region are experiencing a teacher shortage throws even more emphasis on the fact described above, which results in the value of the information growing. It is a fact that the age profile of teachers is skewed toward the older end of the age range in many nations, and there is evidence to suggest that the situation has been becoming worse in recent years.

since a consequence of this, there is a good chance that the future supply of teachers will be impacted, since a proportionately higher number of instructors will retire in any given year. In addition, over the last several years, the size of the average wage has drastically shrunk, which has led to a major decline in the relative allure of the job. Other research reveals that, at least in certain countries, a considerable fraction of the teaching workforce does not possess a normal teaching license, and the proportion of 'out-of-field' teaching assignments is remarkably high in many major subject areas. In addition, there is a significant number of teaching assignments that are not related to the subject matter being taught. In view of these developments, the conduct of study to determine which may be the most effective ways for controlling the supply and demand of teachers seems to be highly warranted. It has been feasible to discover some empirical data inside this study, which has assisted us in identifying a comprehensive set of policies that should be given significant attention in the management of teacher supply and demand.

A significant conclusion is that the policy instruments employed on the supply side or in the structure of schooling markets are significantly more promising in terms of increasing student outcomes than the policy tools used on the demand side. This is an important discovery. To be more specific, the research demonstrates that broad class size reductions, the primary policy

instrument on the demand side, do not have a significant effect and are exceedingly costly to implement. There is a growing consensus around the idea that class size reductions should target those who stand to benefit the most from them. This is due to the fact that there are circumstances in which reductions in class size are beneficial (for instance, at lower grade levels or for students with lower incomes and more disadvantages), as well as the fact that large-scale reductions are too expensive to implement. It was found that supply-side policies, such as those that make teaching a more attractive profession, as well as their influence on the structure of schooling markets, such as those that decentralize decision-making, were more likely to be successful in enhancing teaching quality.

It seems from the evidence that pertains to the career choices of aspiring teachers, tutors, and previous teachers that these individuals react to incentives. Who enters into teaching, who remains in teaching, and who returns to teaching after taking a sabbatical from the profession are all heavily influenced by factors such as salaries and opportunity costs. Other considerations, such as the possibilities available within the teaching profession, working conditions, teacher training and certification processes, and the general standing of the teaching profession all play a significant part in the hiring choices of potential teachers. In addition, there is more research that implies a person's personal qualities have a significant impact on their responsiveness to incentives. It is during the first few years of a teacher's employment that they are most likely to abandon the teaching profession. Teachers who are more academically brilliant or who work in sectors that give greater prospects outside of education are more likely to quit the profession altogether and are also less likely to return to teaching after leaving the field. One such fundamental difference between men and women is how they respond to monetary and non-monetary rewards. The creation of policy should strongly consider these facts in light of their crucial significance.

The problem for those responsible for setting policy is to devise incentives that will attract prominent applicants and former teachers to the pool of individuals who want to teach, to weed out those who do not possess the abilities necessary for teaching, and to keep excellent instructors who are already working in the profession. In order to accomplish this objective, the administrators of the educational system need to devise a system of incentives that will mold the teaching workforce into one that has the right distribution of experience and credentials. For instance, given the higher rates of young, outstanding teachers leaving the field, the pay structure should try to lower the number of instructors who leave the profession in the early years of their employment. In addition, since the employment of women is essential to the maintenance of the teaching workforce, the incentive structure must take into consideration the fact that women often quit

the field due to family responsibilities. It is for this reason that it would be desirable to expand the "flexibility" of the profession or to offer services such as child care. In the same vein, the training and certification of teachers is also an essential component. It is ideal to implement licensing criteria that prohibit people who do not have the requisite abilities to teach successfully from pursuing a career in education. Incentives to encourage prospective teachers to get a high-quality education are also essential. Reforms in this area can include setting higher admission criteria for programs that educate teachers, making the content of courses more challenging, and assessing candidates' basic competencies as well as their subject-matter competency for certification. A loosening of the license requirements would be a good addition to the regulations, especially for those who show promise in other ways. In a similar vein, professional development has been highlighted as a valuable resource that may provide chances for more experienced teachers to gain new abilities. As a result, it should be utilized as an essential instrument in policies that aim to retain teachers and should be prioritized accordingly. In addition, a plethora of studies emphasize the fact that it is beneficial to undertake efforts to enhance the public image of the teaching profession, indicating that this is something that should be pursued. This simply implies granting greater autonomy to schools and allowing teachers more influence in the classroom. In point of fact, this research brings to light the ever-increasing significance of proper school administration.

It has been shown that the organizational circumstances of schools have an effect on the turnover rate of teachers, and that performance-based accountability systems have the potential to be an alternative that is practical for enhancing educational results. Policymakers are becoming more and more vocal about the need of decentralizing decision-making authority. It is recommended that schools be given greater ability to control concerns such as designing their own recruiting and recruitment procedures, setting compensation levels, incentive structure, assessment methods, or investing in continuing education. These are only some of the difficulties that may be managed with this authority. Specifically, regulations that lead to enhanced recruiting methods are particularly significant since they serve as the connection between compensation schedules and the quality of a teacher's work. The information presented in this paper suggests that current recruiting strategies may not be the best way to correlate teacher compensation to teacher quality.

As a result of this, in order for schools to make progress toward their goal of recruiting and retaining higher-quality teachers, they will need to develop more robust performance incentives for school employees. It's possible that this is part of a larger set of measures that aim to incorporate more aspects of competition into the education industry. In addition, the implementation of productivity-based incentives and increased autonomy in the management of schools, such

elements can include a wider choice of schools, pay differentiation to account for gaps in particular subject areas, grade levels, or regions of the country, and schools directly competing with one another for teachers. In this context, the structure of careers could include compensation that is driven by the market, responsibility that is based on performance, different career routes, and ongoing professional development. It is a commonly held belief that the provision of incentives is critical to the achievement of goals in education as well as in other spheres of life. In addition, with regard to the administration of the supply and demand of teachers, education policy seems to be moving in the direction of deregulatory practices, with an increased focus on a variety of incentive-based systems. Along these same lines, officials underline the need of openly tying such incentive schemes to the performance of students, since this is the ultimate purpose of any education system. In addition to that, this publication offers insight on the existing data availability in the OECD as well as the essential data requirements for future quantitative research. For the purposes of describing the current teaching workforce and developing policies aimed at enhancing educational institutions, the availability of high-quality data is absolutely necessary. For instance, despite the widespread perception that a great number of nations are afflicted by a lack of qualified teachers, there is a paucity of hard data about the nature and extent of the shortages in these nations. The demographic profile of instructors, demand-side parameters (such as student enrollment, composition of the school-age population, instructional time necessary for students, teachers' teaching loads, enrollment rates), and teachers' wages are the areas that are best covered by the data that is currently available.

Conclusion

One of the ultimate aims is to evaluate the status of the data that is now available on educators in the OECD. It is crucial to identify a complete collection of data items that are relevant for future meaningful quantitative research. The outcomes of the study that was carried out in order to assemble this report led to an important discovery: the quality of the teacher is an essential element in deciding how much information a student is able to absorb. As a consequence of this, the process of hiring and keeping highly trained educators is essential to the development of superior educational establishments. As a consequence of the general notion that certain countries in the OECD region are experiencing a scarcity of instructors, the reality that was mentioned above receives even more focus, which ultimately leads to a rise in the value of knowledge. In many nations, the age profile of trainers is skewed toward the older end of the age range, and there is

evidence to indicate that the issue has worsened in recent years. This is a reality that has been observed, but there is also evidence to imply that the problem has worsened in recent years.

since a consequence of this, it is quite probable that the future supply of teachers will be impacted, since a proportionately higher number of instructors will retire in any given year. The size of the average pay has decreased dramatically over the last few years, resulting to a large decline in the relative attractiveness of the profession as a result. In addition, this has led to a considerable fall in the number of people entering the profession. Other research reveals that, at least in certain countries, a considerable fraction of the teaching workforce does not possess a normal teaching license, and the proportion of 'out-of-field' teaching assignments is remarkably high in many major subject areas. In addition, there is a significant number of teaching assignments that are not related to the subject matter being taught. A significant portion of the teaching tasks that are given out are unrelated to the material that is currently being covered in class. In view of these changes, it seems to be highly appropriate to do research in order to discover what would be the most successful ways for controlling the supply and demand of teachers. It has been feasible to discover some empirical data within this research, which has assisted us in identifying a complete set of policies that should be carefully examined in the management of teacher supply and demand. These findings may be found throughout the study.

One of the most important things that we discovered was that the policy instruments that are utilized on the supply side or in the structure of schooling markets are considerably more promising than those that are used on the demand side. This is a significant piece of information. To be more precise, the research suggests that substantial class size reductions, which are the principal policy instrument on the demand side, have no meaningful effect and are too costly to execute. This is because extensive class size reductions include reducing the number of students in each class. There is a growing body of support for the concept that individuals who stand to gain the most from efforts to reduce class sizes should be the focus of such efforts. This is because there are circumstances in which a decrease in class size is desirable (for example, in lower grades or for students with lower incomes and greater disadvantages), and also because it is exceedingly costly to apply discounts on a broad scale. It was discovered that the impacts on the structure of school markets, such as policies that decentralize decision-making, as well as supply-side policies, such as those that make teaching a more attractive profession, are more likely to be effective in enhancing teaching quality. One example of a policy that decentralizes decision-making is a policy that was enacted in the United States.

It would indicate that these people react to incentives about their job choices, based on the facts on the career choices of future teachers, trainers, and previous instructors. Factors such as salary and opportunity costs play a significant role in determining who enters the teaching profession, who remains in the teaching profession, and who returns to teaching after leaving the profession. Other factors, such as the possibilities that are available in the teaching profession, the working circumstances, the teacher training and certification processes, and the overall status of the teaching profession all play a significant influence in the choices that prospective teachers make about whether or not to join the teaching profession. In addition, there is more evidence to show that a person's personal traits have a major influence on the way in which they respond to incentives, and this data is consistent with the hypothesis that these features play a role. The first few years of a teacher's career are the years during which they have the highest probability of leaving the teaching profession. Teachers who are more academically bright or who work in professions that give more options outside of education are more likely to quit the profession entirely and are also less likely to return to the field after leaving it. This is because teachers who are more academically brilliant are more likely to work in fields that provide more chances outside of education. The manner in which men and women react to monetary and non-monetary incentives is yet another significant variation between the sexes. Because of the significant repercussions that these facts have, it is imperative that they be thoroughly considered whenever new regulations are developed.

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